

Short communication

Evaluating dental AI research papers: Key considerations for editors and reviewers

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly used in dental research for diagnosis, treatment planning, and disease prediction. However, many dental AI studies lack methodological rigor, transparency, or reproducibility, and no dedicated peer-review guidance exists for this field.

Methods: Editors and reviewers from the ITU/WHO/WIPO AI for Health – Dentistry group participated in a structured survey and group discussions to identify key elements for reviewing AI dental research. A draft of the recommendations was circulated for feedback and consensus.

Results: The consensus from editors and reviewers identified four key indicators of high-quality AI dental research: (1) relevance to a real clinical or methodological problem, (2) robust and transparent methodology, (3) reproducibility through data/code availability or functional demos, and (4) adherence to ethical and responsible reporting practices. Common reasons for rejection included lack of novelty, poor methodology, limited external testing, and overstated claims. Four essential checks were proposed to support peer review: the study should address a meaningful clinical question, follow appropriate reporting guidelines (e.g., DENTAL-AI, STARD-AI), clearly describe reproducible methods, and use precise, justified, and clinically relevant wording.

Conclusion: Editors and reviewers play a critical role in improving the quality of AI research in dentistry. This guidance aims to support more robust peer review and contribute to the development of reliable, clinically relevant, and ethically sound AI applications in dentistry.

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) can potentially enhance dental and craniomaxillofacial diagnoses, treatment support [1]. Several reviews have highlighted AI's applications in diagnostic imaging [2,3], caries detection [4,5], dental medicine [6], oral cancer [7], periodontology [8], oral and maxillofacial surgery [9], pediatric dentistry [10], orthodontics [11], and in educational [12] and research contexts [13].

Despite its potential, AI dental research often lacks methodological rigor and reporting quality as noted in systematic reviews [4]. Similar to any health technology, AI requires evaluation through clinical study designs and evidence-based principles to ensure its safety, effectiveness, and applicability [14]. However, many technical papers published in clinical journals have failed to address their clinical relevance [4]. Regardless of technical complexity, clinicians and reviewers must assess an AI study's clinical utility and impact on patient care or improvement

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in the methodology. For example, a radiology paper does not require a full understanding of particle physics, but must clarify the clinical implications of the findings.

As editors, reviewers, and researchers, we identified key reporting issues in AI manuscripts that can be addressed by peer review. Strengthening peer review is crucial to improving AI research quality, reproducibility, and transparency. This study aims to provide structured recommendations to support editors and reviewers in evaluating AI manuscripts.

2. Methods

We convened members of the ITU/WHO/WIPO Global Initiative on Artificial Intelligence for Health - Dental Diagnostics and Digital Dentistry, a multidisciplinary working group part of a global initiative to advance AI in healthcare by promoting knowledge exchange and technical standards for dental applications. We invited editors and reviewers with experience reviewing AI dental papers to share their insights. Their opinions were collected through a structured survey, followed by group discussions to reach a consensus on the essential elements for reviewing AI research in dentistry. A draft was prepared and circulated among participants.

3. Results

The invited group comprised editors and reviewers from various dental journals. Participants reported contributions ranging from over 400 reviews accredited in ORCID and the Web of Science to up to 120 editor records. Based on their input, four essential checks were identified when reviewing AI manuscripts in dentistry. Based on the participants' input, we summarised the main characteristics of high-quality AI dental research papers and the most frequent reasons for manuscript rejection.

3.1. What are the main characteristics of high-quality AI dental research papers?

- 1. Addresses a real clinical problem and demonstrates novelty or advances in AI methodology:** AI research should address a real clinical problem rather than apply machine learning without a clear purpose. High-quality studies demonstrate originality, offer advancements over existing methods, and provide new insights into AI's role in dentistry. The AI tool should have a well-defined use case and level of deployment to ensure its practical applicability in clinical settings. Additionally, while the clinical impact is important, methodological studies on generalizability, acceptability, and reliability also add value. These methodological studies, for example, how to increase the generalizability of AI models or addressing the issue of multiple annotations in a dataset, should produce findings applicable across use cases, strengthening AI's foundation even without immediate clinical application.
- 2. Follows a robust methodology and ensures transparent reporting:** A strong AI study relies on a robust dataset that is large, well-curated, with high-quality data, and is representative of the intended clinical application. The data sources, pre-processing steps, and annotation processes must be clearly described. External and independent testing (validation), geographically or ideally prospective, is essential to claim the model's generalizability and potential clinical use. Reporting should follow established guidelines such as DENTAL-AI [15], STARD-AI [16], or CLAIM [17] to ensure transparency and adherence to best practices.
- 3. Is reproducible, allowing independent testing of results:** The best indicator of a high-quality AI dental research manuscript is that its results can be independently replicated or tested. This provides transparency and credibility [18]. When essential elements like data or code are missing, the manuscript is more of an advertisement than

verifiable research ("trust me, this research was done!") [19]. By contrast, high-quality AI research allows reproducibility by sharing datasets [20], code [21,22], code and data [23], and a functional demo [24]. The demo is useful when conflicts of interest prevent full-code disclosure. If authors do not intend for their results to be independently reproduced, but still wish to claim novelty, patenting may be a more appropriate route than scientific publication.

- 4. Adheres to ethical guidelines, ensuring fair reporting of AI capabilities:** Reproducibility is not only a marker of high-quality research papers but also a fundamental aspect of ethical research, preventing waste research [25,26] and promoting transparency [27]. Ethical AI studies go beyond technical performance by ensuring responsible and meaningful reporting of findings [28]. Claims must be specific, contextualized, and empirically grounded, avoiding overstatements that could mislead clinicians or patients about unrealistic AI performance. AI performance should be framed within the context of clinical applicability, limitations, and real-world impact, rather than speculative or exaggerated claims of superiority [28]. Additionally, AI results should be compared to human performance without AI to provide a benchmark for their actual contribution and clinical relevance.

3.2. What are the main reasons for AI paper rejection?

- 1. Lack of novelty and clinical relevance:** Many manuscripts apply existing machine learning models to dental datasets without offering meaningful improvement over prior work or addressing a real clinical problem. This includes trivial AI applications that do not demonstrate a benefit to the application of the AI solution, such as no impact on oral disease prevalence, incidence, severity, diagnostic or treatment decisions, or dental coverage, and no comparison of performance to the current standard of care or any improvement.
- 2. Poor methodology and reporting:** Frequent issues include unclear study designs, missing methodological details (e.g., training processes, testing, dataset selection, and computational resources), and lack of transparency in labelling, data sources, and preprocessing steps.
- 3. Insufficient testing and reproducibility:** Many studies lack testing [17] on independent or external datasets, making it difficult to assess the generalizability of the findings. Poor reproducibility due to missing details on model development and unavailable datasets/codes further weakens study reliability.

3.3. Four essential checks for reviewing AI manuscripts

Then, the following suggestions can be made for reviewing dental AI research:

1. What is the research question?

Any research should originate from a relevant clinical problem or question arising from current evidence. The existence of AI alone does not justify its application in every clinical scenario. Reviewers often highlight that many studies lack a well-defined scientific question, fail to compare AI performance against the current standard of care, or offer no meaningful improvement over conventional methods [29].

A common issue in AI dental research is reporting technical performance metrics without contextualizing their clinical significance [14]. For instance, an increase in specificity from 93 % to 97 % may appear remarkable; however, without explaining its impact on diagnostic likelihood ratios, treatment decisions, or how it compares to existing diagnostic methods, its real-world value remains unclear. Does this improvement reduce unnecessary treatments? Does this change clinical outcomes? Reviewers should ensure that the reported metrics are not only statistically significant, but also clinically meaningful in guiding diagnosis and patient care.

AI research in dentistry should target real clinical challenges, ensure that the proposed solutions offer measurable benefits, and avoid

overstating the usefulness of the technology without appropriate external testing [14].

2. Is the AI Manuscript Following the Right Reporting Guidelines?

Most issues in dental AI manuscripts can be avoided by proper adherence to reporting guidelines. The editors and reviewers should verify whether the authors have followed the appropriate guidelines. Frameworks like STARD-AI [16] for diagnostic accuracy, CLAIM for AI in medical imaging [17], and TRIPOD-AI for prediction models [30] help ensure key methodological details are transparently reported.

In addition to these general guidelines, DENTAL-AI [15] serves as a dental-specific framework for all AI research, addressing discipline-specific considerations that are often overlooked in general AI reporting guidelines. Also, Kolbinger et al. provided different guidelines for the phase of AI development: preclinical, translational, or clinical [31]. Table 1 summarizes the key AI reporting guidelines and their scope to help researchers and reviewers select the most appropriate guidelines for their study.

3. Is the Methodology Transparent and Reproducible?

Table 1

Overview of key AI reporting guidelines for dental and medical AI research.

Acronym	Purpose	Key Features and Reference
DENTAL-AI (D)	Dental AI research	Covers planning, conducting, and reporting in dentistry [15].
DentalCOMS (D)	Technical metrics to report in dental computer vision	Eight Core Outcome Measures Set (COMS) for reporting AI-driven computer vision studies in dentistry [38].
STARD-AI	Diagnostic accuracy studies	Focuses on transparency and completeness in AI diagnostic accuracy research [16].
CLAIM	Medical imaging AI	Ensures key study parameters are reported for AI in medical imaging, promoting transparency and reproducibility [17].
TRIPOD-AI	Prediction model studies	Extension of TRIPOD, guiding transparent reporting for AI-based predictive models in healthcare [40].
TRIPOD-LLM	Studies using large language models (LLMs)	Extension of the TRIPOD + AI for LLMs in biomedical applications [41].
CONSORT-AI	AI in clinical trials	Extension of CONSORT, specifying AI-related considerations in randomised controlled trials [42].
SPIRIT-AI	Clinical trial protocols	Companion to CONSORT-AI, focusing on reporting protocols for AI-related clinical trials [43].
MI-CLAIM	Clinical AI modeling	Outlines minimum reporting requirements for any AI model [44].
MINIMAR	Classification models	Ensures transparency in classification models [45].
REFORMS	ML studies	Checklist with 32 questions and guidelines to ensure validity, reproducibility, and generalizability in ML-based research [46].
STANDING	Health Datasets for AI	29 recommendations to enhance transparency in health datasets and mitigate algorithmic bias in AI [47].
Dental Ethical-AI (2, D)	Ethics	Addresses ethical principles including transparency, privacy, and accountability in Dental AI Research [48].
FUTURE-AI (3)	Ethics	Promotes fairness, usability, robustness, and explainability in AI systems, focused on deployment [49].
DECIDE-AI	AI decision support systems	Reporting guideline with 17 AI-specific items (28 subitems) and 10 generic items for early clinical studies of AI-based decision support systems [50].

(1) Checklist; (2) Framework & Checklist; (3) Guiding principles; (D) Dental-specific.

Even if a paper declares adherence to a reporting guideline, reviewers must ensure that the key methodological details are properly described, allowing for the validity and reproducibility of the findings [32]. Issues with transparency, particularly data [33] and codes [34], limit the reproducibility of the results and create a barrier to clinical implementation [27]. When reviewing the AI manuscripts, we consider the following:

- Study design transparency:** Ensure that the study explicitly states its design (e.g., retrospective, prospective, cross-sectional) and aligns with the research questions. If key methodological elements are missing, request clarification.
- Data source and preprocessing:** Check whether the authors describe the origin of their dataset, selection criteria, and preprocessing steps (e.g., augmentation and normalization). If not, we asked for a detailed dataset description to assess the potential biases.
- Model development and validation:** The training and testing procedures of the AI model were thoroughly documented. If external testing is missing, we suggest including an independent dataset to evaluate generalizability.
- Reproducibility:** Encourage authors to share sufficient methodological details, including data availability (ideally) or dataset metadata (mandatory), using the FAIR framework [35], model parameters, and model code (if no conflict of interest is declared) or a minimal functional demo, to facilitate replication by other researchers.

4. Ensuring accurate and responsible wording in AI reporting

- Fair comparison with clinical standards:** Does the study compare AI performance with existing clinical methods fairly and transparently? AI should not be presented as inherently superior without clear benchmarking against the standard of care. Studies should specify the comparison group, data conditions, and clinical context rather than making vague claims of superiority [28].
- Differentiating diagnosis from prediction:** AI studies often conflate diagnostic models (which assess whether a disease is present) with prognostic models (which predict future health outcomes) [36,37]. Reviewers should ensure that the authors correctly classify their AI models and that the conclusions align with the type of model being evaluated.
- Ensuring standardized and clinically relevant terminology:** AI studies published in dentistry should use established diagnostic and predictive terms to ensure clinicians and the public can accurately interpret findings and compare results with existing standards [38] (e.g., "sensitivity" instead of "recall," "positive predictive value" instead of "precision"). If task-specific metrics such as the F1-score or Dice coefficient are used, the authors must define their clinical relevance and the minimal clinically significant difference being tested [14].
- Proper use of validation and testing terminology:** The term *validation* is no longer recommended [17]; *testing* should be used instead. The authors must clearly define and correctly apply the testing. If validation is performed in addition to testing, including cross-validation, its purpose should be clearly stated (e.g., fine-tuning hyperparameters and early stopping of model fitting). Many AI studies rely solely on retrospective datasets, which may not adequately represent the population to which an AI tool will be applied. This includes situations in which models are trained on imaging datasets from certain equipment and may not perform optimally for images from other vendors. Reviewers should ensure that the authors distinguish between internal testing, external testing (prospective, geographically, and ideally independent), and real-world evaluation to avoid overstating clinical readiness [37].
- Avoiding misuse of the term "Ground Truth":** The term "Ground truth" is often misused when referring to clinician consensus in

subjective diagnoses such as caries detection. In these cases, the term "reference standard" is the appropriate one. Reviewers should ensure that studies avoid implying absolute correctness when the diagnosis relies on expert opinions rather than objective validation.

- F. **Justifying performance claims with real-world context:** Many AI studies in dentistry operate in highly controlled environments, similar to in vitro research, and findings often fail to translate into clinical practice [39]. Reviewers should question whether studies provide sufficient real-world evidence before making claims regarding their clinical applicability. If a model has been tested only on a retrospective dataset, its findings should not be overstated as immediately applicable to clinical decision-making.

4. Discussion

The identified issues highlight broader concerns in the development and evaluation of dental AI research. Many AI dental studies fail to demonstrate clinical relevance, rely on limited datasets, or present optimistic claims without adequate validation. These limitations not only reduce scientific credibility, but also hamper the translation of AI tools into practice. Like any healthcare intervention, AI requires the same level of evidence and validation as other medical technologies. A randomized clinical trial remains the gold standard for assessing whether AI-driven interventions genuinely improve patient outcomes or treatment decisions compared to conventional tools. Claims regarding AI effectiveness must align with the actual level of evaluation and should not prematurely suggest clinical utility. Furthermore, ethical reporting is essential. Reproducibility is a scientific and ethical requirement that reduces research waste and supports transparency. Misleading language, vague performance claims, or unsupported comparisons with human expertise undermine trust in AI applications. Responsible reporting must include clear clinical framing, appropriate comparisons to existing care standards, and a transparent discussion of limitations. Editors and reviewers play key roles in identifying and correcting these issues during peer review. The guidance provided here offers a practical framework for consistently and rigorously assessing AI manuscripts. Table 2 summarizes the essential questions that reviewers and editors should address when evaluating AI dental research.

5. Conclusion

AI can support meaningful advances in dentistry but can only be evaluated with appropriate scientific and ethical standards. Strengthening peer reviews with structured criteria will help ensure the trustworthiness, reproducibility, and clinical relevance of AI research.

Clinical significance

- Artificial intelligence is new and rather complex for the dental community
- Editors and reviewers can benefit from guidance on key methodological items when reviewing dental AI research manuscripts.

Data availability

The survey answers are available as supplementary material.

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Table 2

Key questions for editors and reviewers when assessing AI manuscripts in dentistry.

Main issue	Key questions for reviewers
What is the research question?	Does the study address a clinically meaningful problem, or is it merely applying AI to an already solved or trivial task? Does the study demonstrate a clear and practical impact on clinical decision-making or patient outcomes? Or does it advance the evaluation of AI (method paper)?
Is the AI manuscript following the right reporting guidelines?	Does the paper adhere to established reporting guidelines (e.g., Dental-AI, CLAIM, STARD-AI)? Are critical methodological components properly reported, such as dataset description, performance metrics, and testing details?
Is the methodology transparent and reproducible?	Has the AI model been tested on independent or external datasets? Are the results reproducible, and is the code, model architecture or demo available for verification?
Is the wording accurate, ethical, transparent, and clinically meaningful?	Does the study compare AI performance fairly and transparently to existing clinical standards, avoiding vague claims of superiority? Are validation and testing properly defined, clearly distinguishing between validation, internal testing, external testing, and real-world evaluation? Is the wording precise, avoiding misleading terms such as "ground truth" when referring to subjective diagnoses, and ensuring that claims are justified within the study's real-world applicability?

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sergio E. Uribe: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Manal H. Hamdan:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Nicola Alberto Valente:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Satoshi Yamaguchi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Fahad Umer:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Antonin Tichy:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Ruben Pauwels:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Falk Schwendicke:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

SEU, NAV, SY, FU, MH, RP, and AT declare no conflict of interest. FS is a co-founder of dental Xrai, a startup that uses artificial intelligence to analyze dental radiographs, but the present work was fully independent of this status. All the authors are members of the ITU/WHO/WIPO Global Initiative on Artificial Intelligence for Health – Dental Diagnostics and Digital Dentistry, Munich, Germany.

Supplementary materials

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